

Management of School Climate as a Predictor of Educational Goals' Attainment in Public Secondary Schools in Cross River, Nigeria

Mary Mark Ogbeche

Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education,
University of Calabar, Calabar.

Email: maryogbeche1985@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study investigated the management of school climate as a predictor of educational goals' attainment in public secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. A survey research design was adopted for the study. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The population of the study comprised all the 264 secondary school administrators in all the public secondary schools in Cross River State who were used for the study through the census approach. A validated instrument by two experts of Measurement and Evaluation in the University of Calabar titled: Management of School Climate as Predictor of Educational Goals Attainment Survey (MSCPEGAS) was used for data collection. The instrument was administered to 60 Vice Principals for reliability study. Using Cronbach alpha reliability for analysis, the reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained. The data gathered were analysed using simple linear regression statistics. Findings revealed that academic climate and school community climate significantly predicted educational goals' attainment in public secondary schools. The researcher concluded that effective school climate management is a significant predictor of educational goals attainment in Cross River State public secondary schools. It was recommended, among others, that Principals should establish a friendly atmosphere in the school and eliminate all harsh statements because it can keep teachers away from interacting, participating, sharing experiences and discussing important issues for the achievement of secondary schools' goals in the Cross River State of Nigeria.

Keywords: Attainment, goals, management, school climate, school, secondary.

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Introduction

Many educational systems around the world are facing numerous challenges in an attempt to achieve their predetermined goals and objectives. In African countries, some schools are still experiencing a pandemic outbreak, lack of leadership, vision, mission and goals, obsolete facilities and fraudulent scholarship schemes. Other schools are fraught with erratic power supply, antiquated libraries and cramped accommodation daily. Nigeria is not excluded from these challenges because there are many cases of conflict over limited resources and strikes, staff/student unrest, vandalism and poor school climate which have both a direct and indirect impact on school goals' achievement. The purpose of this paper, therefore, is to project a

positive school climate as the sine qua non for the attainment of public secondary school goals in Nigeria generally and Cross River State in particular.

A goal is a futuristic idea or a desired result envisioned, planned and committed to achieving by a person or a group of people. However, some people endeavour to reach their goals within a finite time by setting deadlines. Others tend to procrastinate or give up in the face of danger. Correspondingly, school leaders are expected to employ their managerial/leadership skills in harnessing educational resources for goals' achievement. This is because educational goals' achievement requires accountability, and cannot be realized in a vacuum (Pobbi, Kor & Opere, 2019). However, through effective management of the learning environment and curriculum leadership, educational goals at the secondary school level are focused on preparing individuals for higher education, equipping school leavers with the needed skills, knowledge and values for effective living within the society (the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014). Leadership in schools at this level is expected to be at its best and of good quality to enhance effective teaching and learning in all subjects. It has to encourage knowledge acquisition, the opportunity for higher education and better learning outcome among the school leavers.

Unfortunately, observation and experience in Cross River State over the years tend to reveal a poor school climate. There appears to be non-collaborative, non-cooperative behaviour by school administrators against teachers, students and their parents. Some parents and students are left out of communication links. There seem to be poor working relations between school and community vis-à-vis unfair enforcement of school rules. The school goals are hardly achieved in some public secondary schools (Pobbi, et al., 2019). However, it is quite appalling that some students in this State find it difficult to perform well in reading, writing and arithmetic. There seems to be a lack of effective school leadership, vision, mission and goals. Some prefer examination malpractice as a shortcut to acquiring the needed number of credits to advance into the higher institution at the expense of learning. Some of the students cannot read, write, spell or pronounce words and sentences correctly. Some cannot answer simple questions, do class or take-home assignments, pass internal and external examinations, relate well with fellow students and teachers, obey simple rules and regulations and constituted authorities. Others flock to miracle centres for exams. These breed multiple illiterates and result in unemployment, over-dependent on parents for stipends rather than making life meaningful for themselves and the society. It is a matter of concern today because many students come out of school and become criminals. Some come out without acquiring employable and life skills. It is expected that during and just before the students leave secondary school, they must have acquired adequate knowledge and skills that will make him or her admissible or employable.

One may however wonder if the rate of failure in internal and external examinations and the inability of the students to achieve expected goals may be attributed to poor leadership practices of the school administrators in secondary school. However, both the Federal and State government have made several attempts by reviewing the secondary school curriculum, providing learning resources as well as organizing seminars and workshops to enhance the training of school personnel on school management models but the problem persisted. Another

dimension of secondary school goals achievement is knowledge acquisition. It is the process of carefully guiding the students by the principal and teachers in absorbing and storing new information in memory, the success of which is often evaluated to ascertain how well the information can later be remembered (retrieved from memory) and utilized.

Knowledge acquisition is accomplished by cooperatively building an organized learning experience in line with the background, grade level, age, orientation and culture of the students. Maxwell, Reynolds, Lee, Subasic and Bromhead (2017) stipulated that this can be done effectively based on the quality and character of school life because the climate is the heart and soul of the school. The process of storing and retrieving information depends heavily on the essence of a school that leads a child, a teacher, and an administrator to love the school and to look forward to being there each school day. This is because a positive school climate helps in the management of the physical learning spaces. Management is seen as a social process concerned with identifying, maintaining, motivating, controlling and unifying formally and informally organized human and material resources within a social system (Adeyemi, 2009). School climate is the feelings and attitudes that are elicited by a school's environment. It encompasses the overall culture of the school (Ugonna, 2016). It is the prevailing atmosphere that coordinates the efforts of people to accomplish goals and objectives using available resources efficiently and effectively in the school organization. According to Ilueme in Ugonna (2016) management of the school, the climate is an organizational process that involves strategic planning of resources with a view of making the people feel mental, socially, emotionally and physically safe in the school system.

One of the most critical dimensions of school climate is the academic climate. Failure to sustain a positive academic climate may likely disrupt school goals attainment. This is because the academic climate is the hub of teaching and learning practices promoted in the school. It is composed of three factors: the leadership roles of the school administrator, the actual methods and instructional practices used by teachers in their classrooms, and teacher's access to training programs they find relevant and helpful, and that is in line with the needs of the school. In schools with a positive climate, however, teachers have ongoing access to training where they can learn new strategies to improve the way they teach. These practices may likely influence student motivation and engagement in the classroom, which in turn may affect academic performance. Maxwell et al. (2017) found that students' perceptions of academic climate significantly explained writing and numeracy achievement and this effect was mediated by students' psychological identification with the school. Furthermore, staff perceptions of school climate explained students' achievement on numeracy, writing and reading tests (while accounting for students' responses).

Similarly, Adeogun and Olisaemeka (2011) found that there is a significant relationship between academic climate, performance and productivity. In the same vein, Konold, Cornel, Jia, and Malone (2018) found that an authoritative academic climate model in terms of structure and student supports were associated with higher student engagement in schools. Moreover, student engagement was directly associated with academic achievement and operated as an intervening factor. This outcome provided new evidence that an authoritative school climate is

associated with high school academic achievement. Correspondingly, Shindler, Jones, Williams, Taylor and Cardenas (2016) found that the use of practices that promote a “psychology of success” lead to greater achievement and higher quality academic climate, and those that promote a “psychology of failure” lead to underperformance.

School community climate is another essential dimension of school climate. The community aspect of school climate refers to the quality of relationships within a school. It also includes the school's connectedness, respect for diversity, and partnerships with other members of the community. The quality of relationships between members of a school (teachers, students, and administrators) influences students' behaviour and achievement. The relationship between a student and their teacher affects their engagement in the classroom, self-esteem, and grades. Treating members of any ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, or religious affiliation equally also means cultivating awareness and appreciation for other cultures in classrooms. The involvement of parents and other community members in school life however requires good communication between parents and school staff, high attendance of school events, the development of mentoring programs, and other initiatives that build relationships between students and the larger community. Omemu (2018) concluded that the situation of community climate and students' academic achievement were not the same in rural and urban schools, mixed and single schools, large and small schools and old and new schools in Edo state public secondary schools.

El-Jajah, Barde and Gishiwa (2018) found that school community climate is high in senior secondary schools in Yobe State. It was equally discovered that there is a significant moderate relationship between social school climate and teachers' effectiveness in senior secondary schools in Yobe State, Nigeria. Greenway (2017) found a statistically significant, positive relationship between community climate and student achievement in middle schools in this region. Similarly, Pobbi, Kor and Opere (2019) found that community climate had a positive and significant effect on the academic performances of students. It was also found that specific community climate factors that influence student performance in ensuring a positive school climate. Macneil, Prater and Busch (2009) found significant differences on all 10 dimensions of the organizational health inventory, with exemplary schools out-performing acceptable schools. Contrarily, no statistical significance was found between exemplary and recognized schools. Statistical significance was found, with recognized schools out-performing acceptable schools on the organizational health dimensions of goal focus and adaptation. Nevertheless, school leaders who for one reason or another have not been effective in keeping their responsibilities, as a result, may not work efficiently in improving school climate because it is assumed that a positive school climate enhances effective teaching and as a result a better performance of student learning. Eboka's (2017) findings revealed that a positive community climate prevails in most public secondary schools in Delta State than a negative school climate. Furthermore, a positive community climate in secondary schools influenced teacher morale resulting in a considerably high level of morale for teacher rapport with the principal, rapport amongst teachers, satisfaction with teaching and teacher status while a moderate level of teacher morale was the result for teacher load.

Statement of the problem

Secondary education in Nigeria is designed by law to achieve the goals of preparing school leavers through knowledge acquisition for higher education and also for useful living within the society. These cardinal goals can only be achieved through an effective school climate for efficient service delivery. Sadly, goal achievement in secondary school has become an issue of great concern in recent times. Observation and researchers' experiences show that the training acquired at the end of secondary education has failed to equip school leavers with the appropriate knowledge and skills to proceed to tertiary institutions or to engage in work. It is observed also that many students cannot read, write, spell or pronounce words correctly because the academic climate is not healthy. Some cannot cope with academic work; hence they do their assignment at will, come to school when they like, some cannot do well in internal and external examinations due to an unhealthy school community climate. This leads to cult activities, stealing, and a high rate of indiscipline among the school leavers. One may however wonder if the rate of failure in internal and external examinations and the inability of the students to achieve secondary school goals may be attributed to poor management of school climate by administrators in secondary school. However, both the Federal and State government have made several attempts by reviewing the secondary school curriculum, providing learning resources as well as organizing seminars and workshops to enhance the training of school personnel on school climate management models but the problem persisted. This has attracted the researchers' attention while addressing the question: To what extent does the management of school climate predict public secondary school goals' attainment in the Cross River State of Nigeria?

Purpose of the study

The study investigated the management of school climate as a predictor of public secondary school goals' achievement in the Cross River State of Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to find out the extent to which:

1. academic climate predicts public secondary school goals attainment;
2. school community climate predicts public secondary school goals attainment

Hypotheses

These hypotheses were formulated to guide the study

1. Academic climate does not significantly predict public secondary school goals attainment
2. School community climate does not significantly predict public secondary school goals attainment

Methods

This research was carried out in Cross River State, Nigeria. It is one of the 36 states in Nigeria located in the southeastern end of the country bordering Cameroon. The state is located on latitude 5° 45' North of the equator and longitude 8° 30' East of the Greenwich meridian. The research design adopted for this study was survey design because the study involved the use of a representative sample from a population and the drawing of inferences based on analysis of available data. The population of the study comprised all the principals in 264 public secondary schools in Cross River State. The Census method was used for the study because the population was not large.

An instrument titled: Transformational Leadership Practices and Secondary School Goals Achievement Scale (TLPSSGAS) was used for data collection. The instrument was a 4-point modified Likert scale. The sub-variables of management of school climate were academic climate and school community climate. Secondary school goals had three sub-variables namely higher education opportunity, knowledge acquisition and learning outcome. Each of these sub-variables was measured using 6 items which gave a total of 30 items. Each item had four response options ranging from Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE) to Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). The items in the instrument were scored as follows: Very High Extent (VHE) =4points; High Extent (HE) =3points; Low Extent (LE) =2points and Very Low Extent (VLE) =1points, for all positively worded items. A reverse score was assigned to all the negatively worded items. The respondents were required to tick one of the four response options against each item to indicate the extent of their agreement or disagreement with the item.

The instrument was validated by two experts in Measurement and Evaluation from the University of Calabar. To determine the reliability of the research instrument, a trial test was carried out. The instrument was administered to 60 Vice principals who were not part of the study sample. Cronbach alpha reliability estimate of the test instrument was done to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. The result of the Cronbach Alpha reliability estimate gave a reliability coefficient of 0.78. This value was high enough to be considered good for the research instrument. The copies of the questionnaire were administered personally by the researchers with the help of three trained research assistants. At the end of the exercise, the two hundred and sixty-four (264) copies of the questionnaire administered were completed and retrieved from the respondents and used for regression analysis.

Results

Hypothesis 1

Academic climate does not significantly predict public secondary school goals' attainment. The first hypothesis states that academic climate does not significantly predict public secondary school goals' achievement in terms of higher education opportunity, knowledge acquisition and

learning outcome. The independent variable is academic climate while the dependent variable is public secondary school goals' attainment assessed from three perspectives (higher education opportunity, knowledge acquisition and learning outcomes). The variables were measured continuously. To test this hypothesis, simple linear regression was applied to the data. The result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 showed that the analysis of variance in the regression output produced an F-ratio of .329 for an opportunity for higher education, 44.780 for knowledge acquisition, and 1.181 for teaching/learning outcomes. These F-ratios were all statistically significant at the .05 probability level. Based on this result, the first null hypothesis was rejected. This means that academic climate significantly predicts public secondary school goals' attainment in terms of opportunity for higher education, knowledge acquisition and learning outcome. The results also showed coefficients of determination (R^2) of .001 for higher education opportunity, .155 for knowledge acquisition, and .005 for learning outcomes. This implies that 0.1%, 15.5%, and 0.5% of the variance in opportunity for higher education, knowledge acquisition, and learning outcomes respectively was accounted for by academic climate. Thus, 99.9%, 99.85% and 99.55% of the variance in opportunity for higher education opportunity, knowledge acquisition, and learning outcomes respectively may be attributed to the effect of other variables extraneous to the study.

Table 1: Summary of simple linear regression analysis on the prediction of public secondary school goals' achievement by academic climate

Secondary school goals Variables	Source of Variation	Sum of Square	Df	Mean square	F-ratio	p	R^2
Opportunity for higher Education	Regression	2.050	1	2.050	.329	.026*	.001
	Residual	1518.946	262	6.225			
	Total	1520.996	263				
Knowledge acquisition	Regression	285.454	1	285.454	44.780	.000*	.155
	Residual	1555.396	262	6.375			
	Total	1840.850	263				
Learning outcomes	Regression	16.009	1	16.009	1.181	.002*	.005
	Residual	3307.584	262	13.556			
	Total	3323.593	263				

Hypothesis 2

School community climate does not significantly predict public secondary school goals' attainment. The independent variable is school community climate while the dependent variable is public secondary school goals' achievement assessed from three perspectives (higher education opportunity, knowledge acquisition and learning outcomes). The variables were measured continuously. To test this hypothesis, simple linear regression was applied to the data. The result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 showed that the analysis of variance in the regression output produced an F-ratio of 9.926 for the opportunity for higher education, 19.343 for knowledge acquisition, and

7.054 for teaching/learning outcomes. These F-ratios were all statistically significant at the .05 probability level. Based on this result, the second null hypothesis was rejected ($p < .05$). This means that school community climate significantly predicts public secondary school goals attainment in terms of opportunity for higher education, knowledge acquisition and learning outcomes. The result also showed coefficients of determination (R^2) of .039 for the opportunity for higher education, .073 for knowledge acquisition and .028 for learning outcomes. This implies that 3.9%, 7.3%, and 2.8% of the variance in opportunity for higher education, knowledge acquisition and learning outcomes respectively was accounted for by school community climate. Thus, 96.1%, 92.7% and 97.2% of the variance in opportunity for higher education, knowledge acquisition, and learning outcomes respectively may be attributed to the effect of other variables extraneous to the study.

Table 2: Summary of simple linear regression analysis on the prediction of public secondary schools' goals' achievement by school community climate

Secondary school goals Variables	Source of Variation	Sum of Square	Df	Mean square	F-ratio	p-value	R^2
Opportunity for higher education	Regression	59.456	1	59.456	9.926	.002*	.039
	Residual	1461.540	262	5.926			
	Total	1520.996	263				
Knowledge acquisition	Regression	135.214	1	135.214	19.343	.000*	.073
	Residual	1705.635	262	6.990			
	Total	1840.850	263				
Learning outcomes	Regression	93.380	1	93.380	7.054	.008*	.028
	Residual	3230.214	262	13.239			
	Total	3323.593	263				

Discussion

One of the findings of this study revealed that academic climate significantly predicts public secondary school goals attainment in terms of opportunity for higher education, knowledge acquisition and learning outcome. The finding indicates that academic climate enables school leaders to enhance their leadership roles for goal attainment. This finding implies that, the higher the level of prevailing academic climate in school leadership, the higher the attainment of public secondary schools' goals could be ensured and vice versa in terms of opportunity for higher education, knowledge acquisition and learning outcome. This finding is in line with the finding of Maxwell et al. (2017) who found that students' perceptions of academic climate significantly explained writing and numeracy achievement and this effect was mediated by students' psychological identification with the school. Similarly, it corroborates the finding of Adeogun and Olisaemeka (2011) who found that there is a significant relationship between academic climate, performance and productivity. In the same vein, it supports Konold, Cornell, Jia and Malone (2018) who found that the authoritative academic climate model in terms of structure and student supports were associated with higher student engagement in schools. The rationale behind this finding is that the academic climate enhances the actual methods and instructional practices used by teachers as well as promotes access to relevant training programs that are in line with the needs of the school for goals attainment.

Another finding of this study revealed that school community climate significantly predicts public secondary school goals' attainment in terms of opportunity for higher education, knowledge acquisition and learning outcome. This indicates that the positive school community climate promoted by the school leaders encourages the quality of relationships within the school regarding connectedness, respect for diversity, and partnerships with other members of the school community. This finding implies that, the higher the level of school community climate in the school system, the higher the attainment of public secondary schools' goals and vice versa in terms of opportunity for higher education, knowledge acquisition and learning outcome. The present finding corroborates that of El-Jajah, Barde and Gishiwa (2018) who found that school community climate was high in senior secondary schools in Yobe State. It was equally discovered that there is a significant moderate relationship between school social climate and teachers' effectiveness in senior secondary schools in Yobe State, Nigeria. The finding also supports Greenway (2017) whose finding showed a statistically significant, positive relationship between school community climate and students' achievement in middle schools in this region. Similarly, it aligns with that of Pobbi, Kor and Opare (2019) who found that school community climate had a positive and significant effect on the academic performances of students. The logic behind this finding is that a positive school community climate enables the principal to employ collaborative and cooperative behaviour in dealing with the teachers, students and parents using open communication links for school goals attainment.

Conclusion

Premised on the findings of this study, it was concluded that management of school climate significantly predicts public secondary school goals' attainment in the Cross River State of Nigeria. Simply put, students' acquisition of requisite knowledge with better learning outcomes and gaining the opportunity for higher education is a function of the prevailing academic and school community climatic condition from the school administrators.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the conclusion of this study

1. The principals and staff must work together as a team to create a good learning environment. They should meet regularly to discuss the lesson plans and activities and to air any concerns they might have.
2. Adequate time should be allotted for effective instructional supervision by school principals for school goals attainment
3. Principals should establish a friendly atmosphere in the school and eliminate all harsh statements because it can keep teachers from interacting, participating and sharing experiences in discussing important issues.

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